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Review Article

**QUALITY OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH BENIGN THYROID
DISORDERS: A LITERATURE REVIEW****Ayah Monaf Al-bayya¹, Hind Abdullah Al Humayani², Alaa Naser Kurdi³, Khalid Ayed Asiri⁴, Mohammed Saeed Bafail⁵, Alaa Essam Alghamdi⁶, Abdulrahman Saleh S Albazie⁷, Saeed Mohammed Saeed Bamani⁸**

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Abstract:

The importance of patient-reported outcomes such as health-related quality of life (HRQL) in clinical research is increasingly acknowledged. In order to yield valid results, the measurement properties of HRQL questionnaires must be thoroughly investigated. One aspect of such a validation process is the demonstration of content validity, i.e. that the questionnaire covers all relevant aspects. We review studies reporting on consequences of thyroid disorders and present the frequency of identified aspects, both overall HRQL issues and classical thyroid symptoms, in order to evaluate which issues are relevant for patients with thyroid diseases. Furthermore, existing questionnaires for thyroid patients are reviewed. A systematic search was performed in the Medline, Cinahl and Psycinfo databases and the reference lists of the relevant articles were hand-searched. Seventy-five relevant studies were identified. According to these studies, patients with untreated thyroid disease suffer from a wide range of symptoms and have major impairment in most areas of HRQL. Furthermore, the studies indicate that impairments in HRQL are also frequent in the long term. Six HRQL questionnaires for thyroid patients were identified. Generally, data supporting the validity of these questionnaires were sparse. According to the available literature, the quality of life of thyroid patients is substantially impaired over a wide range of aspects of HRQL in the untreated phase and continues to be so in many patients also in the long term. Studies systematically exploring the relative importance of these various aspects to thyroid patients are lacking, as is a comprehensive, validated thyroid-specific HRQL questionnaire.

Key Words: *Quality of Life, Patients, Thyroid Disorders, Review.*

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INTRODUCTION:

The evaluation of health-related quality of life (HRQL) implies evaluations of the impact of a disease and its treatment on all relevant dimensions of the patient's life. HRQL measurements usually comprise aspects of physical, mental and social well-being and function. Generally, HRQL is best rated by the patients themselves, usually by means of standardized questionnaires. There are two main types of HRQL measures: disease-specific and generic. Disease-specific questionnaires concern issues of particular relevance for patients with a specific medical condition, whereas generic instruments (e.g. SF-36 or EQ-5D) measure aspects common to most patients. Disease-specific measures often demonstrate greater sensitivity than generic measures, while the latter allow for comparison across diseases and treatments and with scores obtained from the general population. A combination of disease-specific and generic measures is generally advocated because each provides complementary information (1, 2). The importance of involving HRQL aspects in the evaluation of thyroid patients is increasingly recognized (3–5). Several features of thyroid diseases motivate this. First of all, benign thyroid disorders are rarely life threatening, and thus their treatment mainly deals with optimizing the quality of life of the patients. Furthermore, the diseases are common and occur at all ages. Moreover, since many thyroid diseases can be treated in several ways (e.g. radioiodine, medical treatment or surgery), exact knowledge of the impact of each treatment modality on the HRQL of the patients is important. To date, no trial has compared validly the HRQL outcome of different treatments and there is still a well-documented lack of consensus regarding choice of treatment (6–15). The detrimental impact of acute thyroid disease on HRQL is obvious and has been documented in several studies (16–18). However, it is the clinical experience of many endocrinologists that some patients have residual complaints despite adequate medical treatment. Application of valid HRQL measurements is crucial for proper clarification of a number of ongoing debates regarding management of thyroid disorders. For example: do patients with subclinical or mild thyroid dysfunction have symptoms and are they fully alleviated by treatment? Is treatment of hypothyroidism with a combination of thyroxine (T₄) and triiodothyronine (T₃) superior to T₄ alone? Does block-replacement therapy as compared with titration therapy of hyperthyroidism result in improved HRQL? Some of the conflicting data regarding these and numerous other questions might be caused by lack of appropriate outcome measures. To ensure valid assessment of a particular patient population, a number

of requirements in relation to HRQL instruments have to be documented (19–23) First, HRQL deals with the patients' experience of the disease and its impact on their lives, and is therefore best assessed by the patients themselves. Secondly, the instrument should cover all aspects of HRQL that are relevant to the patients (content validity). Thirdly, empirical tests should evaluate whether the questionnaire measures what is intended (construct validity). For HRQL measures, where no external 'gold standard' exists, several approaches to this subject have been implemented: qualitative, cognitive studies exploring patients' understanding of the items or quantitative studies investigating the underlying measurement model. Finally, appropriate measurement properties, including sensitivity and responsiveness, have to be demonstrated; that is, there must be an acceptable ratio between true variance compared with variance due to random error (reliability), the measure must be sensitive to clinically relevant differences and it must be responsive to relevant changes with time. Our review concerns content validity. We present a systematic literature review the purpose of which is to describe complaints and consequences of thyroid disorders found in previous studies.

METHODOLOGY:

Sample

We performed comprehensive search using biomedical databases; Medline, and Pubmed, for studies concerned with placenta previa published between 1975- 2019 in in English language. Keywords used in our search through the databases were as { Quality of Life, Patients, Thyroid Disorders, Review }. More relevant articles were recruited from references lists scanning of each included study.

Analysis

No software was used, the data were extracted based on specific form that contain (Title of the study, name of the author, Objective, Summary, Results, and Outcomes). Double revision of each author outcomes was applied to ensure the validity and minimize the errors.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION:

The literature search

A Medline search on the Medline Subheadings (MeSH) thyroid diseases AND (quality of life OR questionnaires OR psychology OR health status OR psychiatric status rating scales OR brief psychiatric rating scale OR severity of illness index OR patient satisfaction OR psychometrics OR depression OR anxiety OR symptoms [title]) NOT carcinoma,

identified 1015 references. The search was repeated in the Cinahl and Psycinfo databases, identifying a total of 2033 references. The abstracts were reviewed and possibly relevant articles reviewed in full length. Further references were identified through the reference lists of these articles. Thus, 2094 references were screened. We also consulted leading thyroid textbooks and included issues listed within these. Seventy-five of the reviewed references were selected, based on the following criteria: the study population (index patients) should be thyroid patients, and the paper should report on patient-experienced consequences of the thyroid disease. Consequences should be documented either as a reported frequency or a higher score on an HRQL scale compared with individuals without thyroid disease. This means that technical or 'objective' measures like 'digit span test' and 'ankle reflex relaxation time' without a subjective equivalent or reported scale-scores without appropriate control groups were not included. In addition, all measures of symptoms and HRQL impact of thyroid disorders used in these studies were identified.

Identified HRQL aspects and symptoms relevant to thyroid patients

Patients with untreated thyroid disease suffer from a wide range of symptoms and have major impairment in most areas of HRQL. For example, 22–35% of goitre patients, 18–66% of hyperthyroid patients, 7–99% of patients with thyroid associated ophthalmopathy (TAO) and 16–51% of hypothyroid patients experience limitations in usual activities during the untreated phase of their disease. These rather wide ranges are due to different ways of measuring the concepts in the studies, differences in patient populations as well as our categorization of the issues; e.g. the term 'limitations in usual activities' covers a wide range of different activities and includes scales from various questionnaires. There is evidence of impaired general health perception in all patient groups; for patients with goitre, hyperthyroidism and TAO this is evidenced by lower scores on scales measuring general health perception compared with scores in normal controls, and thus no percentage is available, whereas for hypothyroid patients dichotomous variables document that 53–100% of patients conceive their health as impaired. Thus, a substantial proportion of thyroid patients experience limitations in their usual activities, perceive their general health as impaired and have social and emotional impairment. Cognitive problems are also prevalent, as is fatigue. Cosmetic concern is also common for all thyroid patients. However, no study has reported on cognitive dysfunction in patients with

goitre and only one study has reported on fatigue in patients with TAO. Generally, patients with goitre have been the least studied. All the classical symptoms of hyperthyroidism appear to be consistently prevalent in hyperthyroid patients, whereas the classical symptoms of hypothyroidism are more variably present in hypothyroid patients. The latter may, in part, reflect the wide spectrum of clinical presentation of hypothyroidism, with a high frequency of subclinical dysfunction.

Persistent HRQL impairment is very frequent among patients with both hyper- and hypothyroidism. About half of the patients have reduced overall quality of life and general health, limitations in usual activities as well as social and emotional problems. Two-thirds are fatigued and about one-third are anxious and have cognitive as well as sexual problems. Furthermore, classical symptoms of hypothyroidism are very frequent among previously hyperthyroid patients and about one-third have persistent hyperthyroid symptoms. However, the association with actual thyroid status has not been addressed in this study. Hypo- or hyperthyroid symptoms have not been examined in long-term follow-up studies of hypothyroid patients and no study has examined the long-term HRQL outcome of goitre treatment. However, there is a general lack of detailed clinical description of the phenotypes of many of the patient populations in these studies and therefore some of the patients classified as hypothyroid may, in fact, be treated goitre patients.

Available thyroid HRQL questionnaires

We have identified six thyroid HRQL questionnaires (24–29). In addition, various symptom indices (30–43), most of which were physician administered, and one satisfaction-questionnaire (29) have been published. The present review will focus on the six HRQL questionnaires but results from studies using the symptom indices are presented in Tables 2 and 3. All the identified HRQL questionnaires target particular thyroid conditions and are not applicable across conditions. No questionnaire measuring the symptoms or impact of non-toxic goitre has been identified.

Hyperthyroidism questionnaires

The Hyperthyroidism Complaint Questionnaire (HCQ) measures residual complaints and psychosocial sequelae in patients treated for hyperthyroidism (24). Thirty-one dichotomous (present/not present) items are summarized in one overall score. Of these, eleven items concern physical symptoms, six are about emotional distress, six evaluate fatigue, and three

concern cognitive function whereas existential problems, sleeping problems, anxiety, sexual function and social function are covered by one item each. The development was based on interviews with a small sample of patients with hyperthyroidism, but no documentation of this has been published. Data from a questionnaire study of 303 formerly hyperthyroid patients were analysed for the purpose of item-reduction (i.e. eliminating items with poor measurement properties or yielding little additional information) yet all items were retained based on an argument that they all contributed to the internal consistency of the scale. Cronbach's α (cf.) was 0.93. Correlations between individual items and the overall score were generally low, some as low as 0.21, suggesting problems with uni-dimensionality (i.e. the assumption that all items in a scale measure an underlying construct, and can therefore be summarized into one overall scale). Thus, the appropriateness of collapsing all items, despite the dissimilarity of the covered issues, into one single score is unknown. There was a significant relationship between scores on the HCQ and the degree of self-reported thyroid dysfunction but no further description of the validity of the instrument has been provided. The HCQ has not been used in any subsequent study and apparently is available in Dutch only.

Questionnaires for patients with thyroid-associated ophthalmopathy

The Graves' Ophthalmopathy Quality of Life Questionnaire (GOQOL) is a disease-specific HRQL instrument for patients with TAO (25, 44, 45). The development was based on a review of existing eye HRQL measures, as well as open-ended questionnaires from 24 patients. It has been pretested in 8 patients. A detailed description of these content validity studies has not been published. The GOQOL consists of 16 items sub-divided into two scales: 'visual functioning' and 'appearance'. Subsequent studies comprising 70–164 well-described patients have shown excellent reliability (25, 44), supported its construct validity (25, 44, 45), and demonstrated good responsiveness (45). According to the developers, the GOQOL is available in six languages (46). However, to our knowledge, the only published validation study regards the Dutch version.

Tehrani and colleagues (26) have also developed a 90-item TAO-specific HRQL instrument in German. Its development was based on contributions from clinicians and was without any patient input. In a study of 104 patients undergoing surgery, the developers found Cronbach's α as low as 0.63 for the 90-item total score. Given the large number of items, this is a low

reliability. No construct validation has been performed, but the low internal consistency reliability suggests lack of uni-dimensionality. In validity analyses, the score did not correlate with clinical variables. Thus, these results do not lend strong support for the reliability and validity of this measure.

Hypothyroidism questionnaires

The Chronic Thyroid Questionnaire (CTQ) is a hypothyroidism *and* patient-specific HRQL questionnaire. It consists of 104 items, each representing a specific complaint, covering four domains: 'physical complaints', 'mood and emotions', 'energy and general well-being', and 'cognitive complaints' (27, 47). The development of the CTQ was quite thorough. Based on a literature review, a list of symptoms or problems related to hypothyroidism, potentially responsive to treatment and likely to influence the quality of life of the patients was generated (27). This list was expanded through interviews with endocrinologists and patients. The scoring of the CTQ is unusual: of the 104 complaints, each patient identifies applicable items and rates the degree of discomfort represented by these items. Thus, for a patient with two of the 104 complaints, the instrument consists of two items, whereas a patient with 22 complaints rates 22 items. This approach increases the potential sensitivity of the measure to improvements in the individual patient, but it makes between-patient comparisons and interpretations of what is actually measured difficult and new complaints arising from intervention are ignored in longitudinal studies. We could not identify any studies validating the resulting questionnaire.

The Thyroid Symptom Questionnaire (TSQ) consists of twelve items: six items on cognitive complaints, five items on physical symptoms and one item on fatigue, summarized in one overall score (28). The items were selected on the basis of patient responses to a notice in the British Thyroid Foundation newsletter, inviting patients to tell about persisting complaints despite replacement therapy with L-thyroxine. Moderate correlations with the generic HRQL questionnaire General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12) were found, but no other evidence of validity has been presented.

Recently, a new hypothyroidism-specific HRQL questionnaire has been developed: the Underactive Thyroid-Dependent Quality of Life Questionnaire (ThyDQoL) (29). ThyDQoL is an 18-item questionnaire measuring the impact of hypothyroidism on various domains of HRQL: overall quality of life (two items), limitations in usual activities (six items),

social function (four items), fatigue (two items), emotional well-being (two items), sexual function, cosmetic complaints, weight problems, and bodily discomfort (one item each). Items are scored individually in a two-step procedure: both impact and importance of the items are rated, and the item score is derived by the multiplication of these two ratings. No multi-item scales are constructed. Problems with this approach are the reduced inter-individual comparability of the measure and the sensitivity to a confounding effect of coping. Content validity was ensured by interviews with 38 hypothyroid patients. However, a quarter of the patients had hypothyroidism secondary to treatment of other thyroid disorders. No information regarding the time since diagnosis or the present thyroid status of the interviewees is provided; all patients, except one, were undergoing treatment with L-thyroxine. Measurement properties (dimensionality, reliability, construct validity, sensitivity, and responsiveness) have not yet been evaluated.

Comparison of the questionnaires

The CTQ includes items relating to a wide range of the identified issues. However, since these assessments are based on one single item, the reliability is probably low for each issue. The well-documented GOQOL questionnaire, which is concerned very specifically with the limitations and social/cosmetic consequences of TAO, covers only three of the identified issues, but since each issue is assessed by multiple items, reliability is probably high. Questionnaires like the HCQ and TSQ produce an overall score, but if the set of issues covered are multidimensional, one overall score might not be the best way of summarizing results. For example, the HCQ combines existential problems and hand tremor into the overall scale score. Regarding HCQ, the lack of items tapping hypothyroid symptoms renders it less suitable for follow-up studies, considering the high frequency of these symptoms among patients treated for hyperthyroidism. None of the hypothyroidism questionnaires consider hyperthyroid symptoms, which might also (albeit not yet studied) be present as a result of the treatment of these patients. This is probably especially important if the measure were to be used for evaluation of the presently intensely discussed issue of T₃-supplementation in hypothyroid patients, in view of the expected higher degree of fluctuations in the serum-concentration of T₃. The ThyDQoL is concerned with more generic aspects of HRQL but, like the CTQ, it is prone to random error due to the use of only single items.

CONCLUSION:

According to the available literature, HRQL impairment in patients with benign thyroid disorders is prevalent, both in the untreated phase and in the long term. A wide range of problems has been reported, covering both generic and specific aspects of HRQL. However, many of the studies are small and use unvalidated measures. Most of them lack a thorough clinical description of the patients and include patients covering a wide range of phenotypes and aetiological dissimilarities. No available questionnaire has the potential to cover all aspects relevant to patients in longitudinal studies, where individual patients may shift from one thyroid state to another as a result of natural history or treatment. The available questionnaires lack documented coverage of relevant HRQL issues and, apart from the GOQOL, they all lack a thorough validation. With this review, we have identified the possibly relevant issues reported in the literature. These data are valuable as a basis for the development of HRQL questionnaires possessing content validity. The next step towards valid measures of disease-specific HRQL in thyroid patients would be to test the relevance of the issues presented here among samples of experts as well as properly characterized thyroid patients.

REFERENCES:

1. GuyattGH, Feeny DH & Patrick DL. Measuring health-related quality of life. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 1993;118:622–629.
2. HaysRD. Generic versus disease-targeted instruments. In *Assessing Quality of Life in Clinical Trials* pp 3–8. Eds P Fayers & RD Hays. Oxford: Oxford University Press 2005.
3. LadensonPW. Psychological well-being in patients. *Clinical Endocrinology* 2002;57:575–576.
4. AbrahamPA, Venell A, Watson WA, Park CM, Bevan JS. Antithyroid Drug Regimen for Treating Graves' Hyperthyroidism (Cochrane Review) *The Cochrane Library* issue 3. Chichester UK: John Wiley & Sons Ltd. 2004.
5. RomijnJAS, Smit JW & Lamberts SW. Intrinsic imperfections of endocrine replacement therapy. *European Journal of Endocrinology* 2003;149:91–97.
6. BennedbaekFN, Perrild H & Hegedüs L. Diagnosis and treatment of the solitary thyroid nodule. Results of a European survey. *Clinical Endocrinology* 1999;50:357–363.
7. BennedbaekFN & Hegedüs L. Management of the solitary thyroid nodule: results of a North American survey. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism* 2000;85:2493–2498.

8. BhagatMCDhaliwal SS Bonnema SJ Hegedüs L & Walsh JP. Differences between endocrine surgeons and endocrinologists in the management of non-toxic multinodular goitre. *British Journal of Surgery*2003901103–1112.
9. BonnemaSJBennedbaek FN Wiersinga WM & Hegedüs L. Management of the nontoxic multinodular goitre: a European questionnaire study. *Clinical Endocrinology*2000535–12.
10. BonnemaSJBennedbaek FN Ladenson PW & Hegedüs L. Management of the nontoxic multinodular goiter: a North American survey. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism*200287112–117.
11. Escobar-JimenezFFernandez-Soto ML Luna-Lopez V Quesada-Charneco M & Glinoeer D. Trends in diagnostic and therapeutic criteria in Graves' disease in the last 10 years. *Postgraduate Medical Journal*200076340–344.
12. Geelhoed-DuyvestijnPHHaak A Hermans J & van der Heide D. Treatment of hypothyroidism in The Netherlands. Results of a survey of Dutch internists. *Netherlands Journal of Medicine*19893472–80.
13. HaakAGEelhoed-Duyvestijn PH Hermans J & van der Heide D. Diagnosis and treatment of Graves' disease. Results of a survey of Dutch internists. *Netherlands Journal of Medicine*19893464–71.
14. SolomonBGlinoeer D Lagasse R & Wartofsky L. Current trends in the management of Graves' disease. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism*1990701518–1524.
15. WartofskyLGLinoer D Solomon B Nagataki S Lagasse R Nagayama Y & Izumi M. Differences and similarities in the diagnosis and treatment of Graves' disease in Europe Japan and the United States. *Thyroid*19911129–135
16. BianchiGPZaccheroni V Solaroli E Vescini F Cerutti R Zoli M & Marchesini G. Health-related quality of life in patients with thyroid disorders. *Quality of Life Research*20041345–54.
17. ElberlingTVRasmussen AK Felldt-Rasmussen U Hording M Perrild H & Waldemar G. Impaired health-related quality of life in Graves' disease. A prospective study. *European Journal of Endocrinology*2004151549–555.
18. RazviSIngoe LE McMillan CV & Weaver JU. Health status in patients with sub-clinical hypothyroidism. *European Journal of Endocrinology*2005152713–717.
19. FayersPM& Machin D. Quality of Life: Assessment Analysis and Interpretation. Chichester: John Wiley and Sons 2000.
20. StreinerDL& Norman GR. Health Measurement Scales. A Practical Guide to their Development and Use2nd edn. Oxford: Oxford University Press 1995.
21. SprangersMACull A Bjordal K Groenvold M & Aaronson NK. The European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer. Approach to quality of life assessment: guidelines for developing questionnaire modules. EORTC Study Group on Quality of Life. *Quality of Life Research*19932287–295.
22. TestaMA& Simonson DC. Assessment of quality-of-life outcomes. *New England Journal of Medicine*1996334835–840.
23. Assessing Quality of Life in Clinical Trials - Methods and Practice2nd edn. Eds PM Fayers & RD Hays. Oxford: Oxford University Press 2004.
24. FahrenfortJJWilterdink AM & van der Veen EA. Long-term residual complaints and psychosocial sequelae after remission of hyperthyroidism. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*200025201–211.
25. TerweeCBGerding MN Dekker FW Prummel MF & Wiersinga WM. Development of a disease-specific quality of life questionnaire for patients with Graves' ophthalmopathy: the GO-QOL. *British Journal of Ophthalmology*199882773–779.
26. TehraniMKrummenauer F Mann WJ Pitz S Dick HB & Kahaly GJ. Disease-specific assessment of quality of life after decompression surgery for Graves' ophthalmopathy. *European Journal of Ophthalmology*200414193–199.
27. JaeschkeRGuyatt G Cook D Harper S & Gerstein HC. Spectrum of quality of life impairment in hypothyroidism. *Quality of Life Research*19943323–327.
28. SaravananPChau WF Roberts N Vedhara K Greenwood R & Dayan CM. Psychological well-being in patients on 'adequate' doses of l-thyroxine: results of a large controlled community-based questionnaire study. *Clinical Endocrinology*200257577–585.
29. McMillanCVBradley C Woodcock A Razvi S & Weaver JU. Design of new questionnaires to measure quality of life and treatment satisfaction in hypothyroidism. *Thyroid*200414916–925.
30. WayneEJ. The diagnosis of thyrotoxicosis. *British Medical Journal*19544859411–419.
31. CrooksJMurray IP & Wayne EJ. Statistical methods applied to the clinical diagnosis of thyrotoxicosis. *Quarterly Journal of Medicine*195928211–234.

32. Murray IP. The clinical diagnosis of thyroid disease. *Medical Journal of Australia* 1964;138:27–31.
33. Gurney CHall R Harper M Owen SG Roth M & Smart GA. Newcastle thyrotoxicosis index. *Lancet* 1970;2:1275–1278.
34. Benvenega SRuggeri RM Russo A Lapa D Campenni A & Trimarchi F. Usefulness of l-carnitine a naturally occurring peripheral antagonist of thyroid hormone action in iatrogenic hyperthyroidism: a randomized double-blind placebo-controlled clinical trial. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism* 2001;86:3579–3594.
35. Klein ITrzepacz PT Roberts M & Levey GS. Symptom rating scale for assessing hyperthyroidism. *Archives of Internal Medicine* 1988;148:387–390.
36. Wayne E. The assessment of thyroid function. *British Journal of Surgery* 1965;52:717–721.
37. Billewicz WZChapman RS Crooks J Day ME Gossage J Wayne E & Young JA. Statistical methods applied to the diagnosis of hypothyroidism. *Quarterly Journal of Medicine* 1969;38:255–266.
38. Zulewski HMuller B Exer P Miserez AR & Staub JJ. Estimation of tissue hypothyroidism by a new clinical score: evaluation of patients with various grades of hypothyroidism and controls. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism* 1997;82:771–776.
39. Barker DJ & Bishop JM. Computer-based screening system for patients at risk of hypothyroidism. *Lancet* 1969;2:835–838.
40. Gardner MJ & Barker DJ. Diagnosis of hypothyroidism: a comparison of statistical techniques. *British Medical Journal* 1975;2:60–62.
41. Cooper DS Halpern R Wood LC Levin AA & Ridgway EC. l-Thyroxine therapy in subclinical hypothyroidism. A double-blind placebo-controlled trial. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 1984;101:18–24. Canaris GJ Steiner JF & Ridgway EC. Do traditional symptoms of hypothyroidism correlate with biochemical disease? *Journal of General Internal Medicine* 1997;12:544–550.
42. Canaris GJ Manowitz NR Mayor G & Ridgway EC. The Colorado thyroid disease prevalence study. *Archives of Internal Medicine* 2000;160:526–534.
43. Terwee CB Gerding MN Dekker FW Prummel MF van der Pol JP & Wiersinga WM. Test-retest reliability of the GO-QOL: a disease-specific quality of life questionnaire for patients with Graves' ophthalmopathy. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 1999;52:875–884.
44. Terwee CB Dekker FW Mourits MP Gerding MN Baldeschi L Kalmann R Prummel MF & Wiersinga WM. Interpretation and validity of changes in scores on the Graves' ophthalmopathy quality of life questionnaire (GO-QOL) after different treatments. *Clinical Endocrinology* 2001;54:391–398.
45. Wiersinga WM Prummel MF & Terwee CB. Effects of Graves' ophthalmopathy on quality of life. *Journal of Endocrinological Investigation* 2004;27:259–264.
46. Jaeschke RGuyatt G Gerstein H Patterson C Molloy W Cook D Harper S Griffith L & Carbotte R. Does treatment with l-thyroxine influence health status in middle-aged and older adults with subclinical hypothyroidism? *Journal of General Internal Medicine* 1996;11:744–749.
47. Biondi B Palmieri EA Fazio S Cosco C Nocera M Sacca L Filetti S Lombardi G & Perticone F. Endogenous subclinical hyperthyroidism affects quality of life and cardiac morphology and function in young and middle-aged patients. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism* 2000;85:4701–4705.
48. Gerding MN Terwee CB Dekker FW Koornneef L Prummel MF & Wiersinga WM. Quality of life in patients with Graves' ophthalmopathy is markedly decreased: measurement by the medical outcomes study instrument. *Thyroid* 1997;7:885–889.
49. Terwee CWakelkamp I Tan S Dekker F Prummel MF & Wiersinga W. Long-term effects of Graves' ophthalmopathy on health-related quality of life. *European Journal of Endocrinology* 2002;146:751–757.
50. Egle UT Kahaly GJ Petrak F Hardt J Batke J Best J & Rothenbacher M. The relevance of physical and psychosocial factors for the quality of life in patients with thyroid-associated orbitopathy (TAO). *Experimental and Clinical Endocrinology and Diabetes* 1999;107:(Suppl 5):S168–S171.
51. Harrison LC Buckley JD & Martin FI. Use of a computer-based postal questionnaire for the detection of hypothyroidism following radioiodine therapy for thyrotoxicosis. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Medicine* 1977;7:27–32.
52. Escobar-Morreale HF Botella-Carretero JI Gomez-Bueno M Galan JM Barrios V & Sancho J. Thyroid hormone replacement therapy in primary hypothyroidism: a randomized trial comparing l-

- thyroxine plus liothyronine with l-thyroxine alone. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 2005;142:412–424.
53. Zeithofer JS, Saletu B, Stary J & Ahmadi R. Cerebral function in hyperthyroid patients. Psychopathology psychometric variables central arousal and time perception before and after thyreostatic therapy. *Neuropsychobiology* 1984;11:89–93.
 54. Demet MM, Ozmen B, Deveci A, Boyvada S, Adiguzel H & Aydemir O. Depression and anxiety in hyperthyroidism. *Archives of Medical Research* 2002;33:552–556.
 55. Rocky PH & Griep RJ. Behavioral dysfunction in hyperthyroidism. Improvement with treatment. *Archives of Internal Medicine* 1980;140:1194–1197.
 56. Stern RA, Robinson B, Thorne AR, Arruda JE, Prohaska ML & Prange AJ Jr. A survey study of neuropsychiatric complaints in patients with Graves' disease. *Journal of Neuropsychiatry and Clinical Neurosciences* 1996;8:181–185.
 57. Park JJ, Sullivan TJ, Mortimer RH, Wagenaar M & Perry-Keene DA. Assessing quality of life in Australian patients with Graves' ophthalmopathy. *British Journal of Ophthalmology* 2004;88:75–
 58. Braverman LE & Utiger RD Eds. *Werner and Ingbar's The Thyroid - a Fundamental and Clinical Text* 7th edn. New York: Lippincott-Raven 1996.
 59. Ljunggren JG, Torring O, Wallin G, Taube A, Tallstedt L, Hamberger B & Lundell G. Quality of life aspects and costs in treatment of Graves' hyperthyroidism with antithyroid drugs surgery or radioiodine: results from a prospective randomized study. *Thyroid* 1998;8:653–659.
 60. Kathol RG, Turner R & Delahunt J. Depression and anxiety associated with hyperthyroidism: response to antithyroid therapy. *Psychosomatics* 1986;27:501–505.
 61. O'Malley BH, Hickey J & Nevens E. Thyroid dysfunction - weight problems and the psyche: the patients' perspective. *Journal of Human Nutrition and Dietetics* 2000;13:243–248.
 62. Maugeri DM, Motta M, Salerno G, Rosso D, Mazzarella R, Salomone S, Russo MS, Elia G & Panebianco P. Cognitive and affective disorders in hyper- and hypothyreotic elderly patients. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics* 1998; Suppl. 6:305–312.
 63. Trzepacz PT, McCue M, Klein I, Levey GS & Greenhouse J. A psychiatric and neuropsychological study of patients with untreated Graves' disease. *General Hospital Psychiatry* 1988;10:49–55.
 64. Whybrow PC, Prange AJ Jr & Treadway CR. Mental changes accompanying thyroid gland dysfunction. A reappraisal using objective psychological measurement. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 1969;20:48–63.
 65. Radanovic-Grguric L, Filakovic P, Barkic J, Mandic N, Karner I & Smoje J. Depression in patients with thyroid dysfunction. *European Journal of Psychiatry* 2003;17:133–144.
 66. Lee IT, Sheu WH, Liao YJ, Lin SY, Lee WJ & Lin CC. Relationship of stressful life events, anxiety and depression to hyperthyroidism in an Asian population. *Hormone Research* 2003;60:247–251.
 67. Paschke RH, Harsch I, Schlote B, Vardarli I, Schaaf L, Kaumeier S, Teuber J & Usadel KH. Sequential psychological testing during the course of autoimmune hyperthyroidism. *Klinische Wochenschrift* 1990;68:942–950.
 68. Farid MR, Roch-Levecq AC, Levi L, Brody BL, Granet DB & Kikkawa DO. Psychological disturbance in Graves' ophthalmopathy. *Archives of Ophthalmology* 2005;123:491–496.
 69. DeGroot LJ & Jameson JL Eds. *Endocrinology* 4th edn. Philadelphia: WB Saunders 2001.
 70. Wass JAH, Shalet SM, Gale E & Amiel SA Eds. *Oxford Textbook of Endocrinology and Diabetes* 1st edn. Oxford: Oxford University Press 2002.
 71. Kahaly GJ, Hardt J, Petrak F & Egle UT. Psychosocial factors in subjects with thyroid-associated ophthalmopathy. *Thyroid* 2002;12:237–239.
 72. Laurberg P. Hypothyroidism. In *The Thyroid Gland* pp 497–535. Ed. MA Greer. New York: Raven Press 1990.
 73. Jain VK. Affective disturbance in hypothyroidism. *British Journal of Psychiatry* 1971;119:279–280.
 74. Gunnarsson TS, Sjoberg S, Eriksson M & Nordin C. Depressive symptoms in hypothyroid disorder with some observations on biochemical correlates. *Neuropsychobiology* 2001;43:70–74.
 75. Cleare AJ, McGregor A & O'Keane V. Neuroendocrine evidence for an association between hypothyroidism, reduced central 5-HT activity and depression. *Clinical Endocrinology* 1995;43:713–719.
 76. Zettinig G, Asenbaum S, Fueger BJ, Hofmann A, Diemling M, Mittlboeck M & Dudczak R. Increased prevalence of subclinical brain perfusion abnormalities in patients with autoimmune thyroiditis: evidence of Hashimoto's encephalitis? *Clinical Endocrinology* 2003;59:637–643.

77. TrivalleCDoucet J Chassagne P Landrin I Kadri N Menard JF & Bercoff E. Differences in the signs and symptoms of hyperthyroidism in older and younger patients. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*19964450–53.
78. OrgiazziJJ& Mornex R. Hyperthyroidism. In *The Thyroid Gland*pp 405–495. Ed. MA Greer. New York: Raven Press 1990.
79. WilsonWPJohnson JE & Smith RB. Affective change in thyrotoxicosis and experimental hypermetabolism. *Recent Advances in Biological Psychiatry*19614234–243.
80. WallaceJEMacCrimmon DJ & Goldberg WM. Acute hyperthyroidism: cognitive and emotional correlates. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*198089519–527.
81. NordykeRAGilbert FI Jr & Harada AS. Graves' disease. Influence of age on clinical findings. *Archives of Internal Medicine*1988148626–631.
82. TakPPHermans J & Haak A. Symptomatology of Graves' disease and Plummer's disease in relation to age and thyroid hormone level. *Netherlands Journal of Medicine*199342157–162.
83. YonemODokmetas HS Aslan SM & Erselcan T. Is antithyroid treatment really relevant for young patients with subclinical hyperthyroidism? *Endocrine Journal*200249307–314.
84. DavisPJ& Davis FB. Hyperthyroidism in patients over the age of 60 years. Clinical features in 85 patients. *Medicine*197453161–181.
85. WatanakunakornCHodges RE & Evans TC. Myxedema: a study of 400 cases. *Archives of Internal Medicine*1965116183–190.
86. Sait GonenMKisakol G Savas Cilli A Dikbas O Gungor K Inal A & Kaya A. Assessment of anxiety in subclinical thyroid disorders. *Endocrine Journal*200451311–315.
87. OddieTHBoyd CM Fisher DA & Hales IB. Incidence of signs and symptoms in thyroid disease. *Medical Journal of Australia*19722981–986.
88. HarperMB. Vomiting nausea and abdominal pain: unrecognized symptoms of thyrotoxicosis. *Journal of Family Practice*198929382–386.
89. AlvarezMAGomez A Alavez E & Navarro D. Attention disturbance in Graves' disease. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*19838451–454.
90. MonzaniFDe Guerra P Caraccio N Pruneti CA Pucci E Luisi M & Baschieri L. Subclinical hyperthyroidism: neurobehavioral features and beneficial effect of l-thyroxine treatment. *Clinical Investigator*199371367–371.
91. EdenSSundbeck G Lindstedt G Lundberg PA Jagenburg R Landahl S & Svanborg A. Screening for thyroid disease in the elderly. Serum concentrations of thyrotropin and 353'-triiodothyronine in a representative population of 79-year-old women and men. *Comprehensive Gerontology Section A Clinical and Laboratory Sciences*1988240–45.
92. WescheMFBuul MM Smits NJ & Wiersinga WM. Reduction in goiter size by 131I therapy in patients with non-toxic multinodular goiter. *European Journal of Endocrinology*199513286–87.
93. Le MoliRWesche MF Tiel-Van Buul MM & Wiersinga WM. Determinants of long-term outcome of radioiodine therapy of sporadic non-toxic goitre. *Clinical Endocrinology*199950783–789.
94. BonnemaSJNielsen VE & Hegedüs L. Long-term effects of radio-iodine on thyroid function size and patient satisfaction in non-toxic diffuse goitre. *European Journal of Endocrinology*2004150439–445.
95. SchloteBNowotny B Schaaf L Kleinbohl D Schmidt R Teuber J Paschke R Vardarli I Kaumeier S & Usadel KH. Subclinical hyperthyroidism: physical and mental state of patients. *European Archives of Psychiatry and Clinical Neuroscience*1992241357–364.
96. MonzaniFCaraccio N Del GP Casolaro A & Ferrannini E. Neuromuscular symptoms and dysfunction in subclinical hypothyroid patients: beneficial effect of l-T4replacement therapy. *Clinical Endocrinology*199951237–242.
97. ArmisteadSH. Symptoms of non-toxic nodular goitre. *Ulster Medical Journal*197645178–180.
98. PapaACammarota G Tursi A Certo M Montalto M Capelli G de Rosa G Cuoco L Fedeli G & Gasbarrini G. Effects of propylthiouracil on intestinal transit time and symptoms in hyperthyroid patients. *Hepatogastroenterology*199744426–429.
99. FilteauSMSullivan KR Anwar US Anwar ZR & Tomkins AM. Iodine deficiency alone cannot account for goitre prevalence among pregnant women in Modhupur Bangladesh. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*199448293–302.
100. BergGMichanek A Holmberg E & Nystrom E. Clinical outcome of radioiodine treatment of hyperthyroidism: a follow-up study. *Journal of Internal Medicine*1996239165–171.

101. Bommer ME, Eversmann T, Pickardt R, Leonhardt A & Naber D. Psychopathological and neuropsychological symptoms in patients with subclinical and remitted hyperthyroidism. *Klinische Wochenschrift* 1990;68:552–558.
102. Thomsen AF, Kvist TK, Andersen PK & Kessing LV. Increased risk of affective disorder following hospitalisation with hyperthyroidism - a register-based study. *European Journal of Endocrinology* 2005;152:535–543.
103. Perrild HH, Hansen JM, Arnung K, Olsen PZ & Danielsen U. Intellectual impairment after hyperthyroidism. *Acta Endocrinologica* 1986;112:185–191.
104. Jansson SB, Berg G, Lindstedt G, Michanek A & Nystrom E. Overweight - a common problem among women treated for hyperthyroidism. *Postgraduate Medical Journal* 1993;69:107–111.
105. Birring SS, Morgan AJ, Prudon B, McKeever TM, Lewis SA, Falconer Smith JF, Robinson RJ, Britton JR & Pavord ID. Respiratory symptoms in patients with treated hypothyroidism and inflammatory bowel disease. *Thorax* 2003;58:533–536.